

**PUBLIC CONTROL: ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN
PRACTICE.****Gaibullaev Farrukh Yuldashevich,****Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Law****E-mail: E-mail: suxbat0199@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17338430>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 10th October 2025Accepted: 11th October 2025Online: 13th October 2025**KEYWORDS***Public control, offense, interest,
politician, legal features.***ABSTRACT***As a result of this scientific work, opinions were expressed on the main essence of public control and some issues related to its application in the legislation of Uzbekistan. A legal analysis of foreign experience in this regard was also carried out.*

In a number of foreign countries, definitions such as "civil" and "democratic" control, among others, are widely used instead of "public" oversight, encompassing a broader range of relationships.

Regulatory Framework. A study of international experience shows that, with rare exceptions, foreign countries generally lack a single, dedicated legislative act comprehensively and systematically regulating the organization and conduct of public oversight. At the same time, a well-developed system of legal regulation of public and civil oversight exists in various areas of socio-economic and socio-political development, including defense, security, law enforcement, and others. A special place in this system of legislative regulation is occupied by norms aimed at ensuring the transparency of government agencies, realizing the right of civil institutions to receive information from government agencies, and their participation in court proceedings, elections, and referendums, etc. (Great Britain, Belgium, USA, France, Finland, Sweden, Estonia, and others).

Object of Public Oversight. The analysis revealed that specific legislative acts most often specify the activities of state authorities, public administration bodies, and their officials as objects of public oversight. However, in certain areas, the activities of local government bodies, legal entities performing public functions, and other entities, regardless of their organizational and legal form or ownership, are also objects of public oversight.

For example, in Germany, objects of public oversight include the activities of state bodies, public institutions, communities and their associations, research institutions, central scientific organizations, schools, and private law bodies performing public functions. In France, objects of public oversight can include government agencies, courts, banks, and others. In the United States, the institution of civilian oversight applies to police activities. However, in the United Kingdom, as a rule, courts, security services, and intelligence agencies are not objects of public oversight.

Subjects of Public Oversight In foreign countries, citizens, non-profit organizations, public councils, advisory institutions, media outlets, and committees of government agencies (UK, Belgium, USA, France, Germany, etc.) are active participants in public oversight. In the US, public associations, media outlets, volunteers, citizen oversight boards, citizen auditors, and others are active participants in public oversight.

Forms of Public Oversight. In foreign countries, depending on the legal system, form of

government, and state of development of civil society, a wide variety of forms of public oversight are used: public hearings (consultations, discussions), public audits (investigations), citizen observation, inquiries, public monitoring (audits), public opinion polls, public legislative initiatives, public oversight bodies, journalistic investigations, public expert review, and hearings of reports (of officials), etc.

For example, in the US, a widely used form of public oversight is citizen observation, which involves the participation of members of the public as observers during the review and investigation of citizen complaints by government agencies. A fairly common form of public control is public legislative initiative, which involves mandatory consideration (but not adoption) by parliament of draft laws that have collected the signatures of a certain number of citizens (Brazil, Germany, USA, Spain, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Switzerland).

Public oversight and advisory bodies (public chambers, public councils, commissions) are a recognized institution of public oversight in the international community (France, Great Britain, the USA, Austria, Brazil, the Netherlands, Greece, Poland, and the Russian Federation). They conduct research and prepare reports on national policy issues and involve the direct participation of public oversight bodies in the work of collegial bodies specifically created by government agencies.

Public Oversight Results. In the vast majority of countries, public oversight results are advisory in nature. However, in cases where public oversight reveals violations, the materials may be transferred to law enforcement agencies for appropriate action. An important mechanism for implementing the results of public oversight is a system of measures to shape public opinion (using the media and other means) on issues that have become the subject of relevant oversight activities. Experience from other countries also shows that some countries have established additional measures to ensure the effectiveness of public oversight, such as mandatory review by government agencies of the results of oversight activities (France, etc.).

References:

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